

Performance Investigation of Di-Diesel Engine with Combined Neem and Pongamia Oil Blends

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ABSTRACT

In now a day we are finding that the bio-Fuels utilization has been increased a lot since the depletion of fossil fuels. Many researchers had worked on the different engines by using only one bio fuel as the fuel for their engines. In this research work two bio oils (biodiesel) has been used to run the engine. In this paper neem oil and Pongamia oils are used by varying percentage of 5% with these two oils mixing them with diesel. In this paper performance of DI diesel engine was used and keeping Neem oil as constant and Pongamia has been varied by 5% parentage. The performance parameters of the test on DI diesel engine Viz. Brake Power, Brake thermal efficiency, Mechanical efficiency, Mass of fuel consumption are represented.

Key-words: Bio-Fuels, Bio-Oils, Neem Oil, Pongamia Oil, Two Oil Blends.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important elements that effect world's economy and sustainability of petroleum resources, which is the main source of world energy supply. However, the world energy demand is increasing rapidly due to excessive use of the fuels and limited availability of petrol supplies. World is currently facing with the crisis of fossil fuel depletion. The increasing demand of petroleum in developing countries like China, Russia and India has increased oil prices [1]. Petroleum fuel used in diesel engines, which has a wide range of use in many sectors like electricity production, transportation of passengers, goods, industrial and agricultural activities. With a situation that demand cannot be met by petroleum based fuels, all the sectors that contributed by oil based energy will negatively be effected. With any probable petrol crises, for all the sectors the alternative fuel is vital area to be developed [2].

Vegetable oils present a very hopeful substitute fuel to diesel, since they are renewable, biodegradable and clean burning, having properties similar to that of diesel. They provide similar power output with slightly lesser thermal efficiency due to their lesser energy content compared to diesel [3]. Bio diesel, produced from different vegetable oils (soybean, rapeseed and sunflower etc.), have been used in internal

combustion engines without major variations, with only slightly decreased performance [4].

Nowadays, global warming caused by CO₂ is the main climatic problem in the world. Therefore, environment safeguarding is important for the future. The biodiesel are made from renewable sources, they are more convenient to protect environment from undesirable emissions. Biodiesel is an ecological and non-hazardous fuel with low emission values, and therefore it is environmentally valuable.

Biodiesel can be produced from various feedstock's. A chemical process called transesterification whereby glycerine is separated from the fat or vegetable oils used to produce biodiesel. After the chemical process, two products are left behind: methyl esters (the chemical name for biodiesel) and glycerine (a valuable by product usually sold to be used in soaps and other products). The usage of biodiesel does not require any changes in the fuel distribution infrastructure, and it is competitive with petroleum-derived diesel fuel. Furthermore, it biodegrades much more rapidly than petroleum diesel fuel. Thus, considerable environmental benefits are provided [5]. Many investigators [6-11] have studied biodiesel fuels as an alternative energy source for IC engines. Combustion emission

levels for biodiesel are more suited compared with those for the petroleum based diesel fuel.

Investigation on the pongamia oil and neem oil are done separately and are reported. The results are convincing to be used as the alternative fuels for the next generation [12-13]. Taking a step ahead the current work deals with the blending two oils in diesel i.e blending the Pongamia oil in various ratios by keeping the neem oil 5% as fixed one in diesel.

Experimental Set-up

Table 1 specification of engine.

Make	Kirloskar
Out put	14 bhp
Ac generator capacity	10 ka 440v 50 hz 3phase
Bore and stroke	87.5mmx110mm
speed	1500rpm
compression ratio	17.5:1
Torque arm distance	0.3
starting	hand cranking

For running diesel engines (ci) bio-diesel has been used. Bio-diesel with different blends had been used to run the engine. Blending proportions are as follows. Hear Neem oil and Pongamia oil has been used. Two oils are blended with diesel in different rations like, n5p5,n5p10, n5p15, n5p20,n5p25 remaining is diesel(in n5p5 10% is neem oil and 5% is Pongamia oil and remaining 90% is diesel and n5p10 contains 5% of neem oil and 10% of Pongamia oil and remaining is 85% is diesel). This oil blends are used to run the engine and conducted performance test on that engine.

Table 2 blending rations of bio-oils with different ratios.

Neem oil %	Pongamia oil %	Diesel %
5	5	90
5	10	85
5	15	80
5	20	75
5	25	70

RESULTS AND DECOCTIONS

The performance test results are as follows first brake power is calculated from readings obtained while running the engine with n5p5 blend and remaining blends as follows N5P10, N5P15, N5P20 and N5P25. Performance test consists of Brake Power, Brake Thermal Efficiency, Mechanical Efficiency and Mass of Fuel Consumed these results are calculated and graphs are plotted. The Properties of oils are as tabulated as follows

Table 3 Properties of fuels.

[1] Properties	[2] Diesel	[3] Neem oil	Pongamia oil
Density	840	[4] 919	924
viscosity at 40°C, mm ² /s	2.6	[5] 35	40.2
[6] calorific value, kJ/kg	[7] 42850	[8] 31142	36601

The schematic graph shows the relationship between brake power and electrical load. Taking electrical load on x-axis and brake power on y-axis. At 1.5 kw n5p15 and n5p25 is giving batter brake power and at 3 kw load n5p5 is giving batter performance at the same time n5p20 and n5p25 is also giving the batter performance compared with n5p10 and n5p15. At 4.5 kw n5p5 and n5p20 are showing good performance. At 6 kw n5p25 is showing very poor performance compared with n5p5, n5p10, n5p15 and n5p20. At 7.5 kw also n5p25 is showing very poor performance compared with n5p5, n5p10, n5p15 and n5p20. From this graph we can understand that n5p5 is giving battered result compared with n5p10, n5p15, n5p20 and n5p25 oil blends.

The schematic graph shows the relation between brake thermal efficiency and electrical load. Taking electrical load on x-axis and brake thermal efficiency on y-axis. At 1.5 kw n5p15 and n5p25 is giving batter brake thermal efficiency while comparing them with n5p5, n5p10, n5p20. At 3 kw we can find that n5p5 is giving batter brake thermal efficiency at the same time n5p20 is also giving the batter performance. At 4.5 kw of

electrical load n5p25 is giving poor performance compared with n5p5, n5p10, n5p15 and n5p20. At 6 kw n5p25 is giving poor performance compared with n5p5, n5p10, n5p15 and n5p20. At 7.5 kw all the blends are giving the same output. From this we can say that n5p5 is giving better performance on all loads. Compared with other blends.

The schematic graph shows the relation between mechanical efficiency and electrical load. Graph is plotted taking electrical load on x-axis and mechanical efficiency on y-axis. At 1.5 kw n5p15 and n5p25 are giving better performance compared with other blends. At 3 kw n5p20 and n5p25 are giving better performance compared with other blends. At 4.5 kw n5p20 is giving better performance compared with other blends. At 6 kw n5p5 and n5p25 are showing poor performance while compared with other blends. And at 7.5 kw also we observed that n5p5 is giving poor performance compared with other blends. On an average n5p25 is giving better performance in all electrical loadings.

The schematic graph shows the relation between mass of fuel consumed and electrical load. Graph is plotted taking electrical load on x-axis and mass of fuel consumed on y-axis. In all the electrical loads we can find N5P5 is having less fuel consumption compared with other blends. N5P25 is consuming more amount of fuel compared with other blends.

CONCLUSIONS

From the performance characteristics of blends we observed that N5P5 blend is giving good brake power, good brake thermal Efficiency, lesser Mechanical Efficiency and less fuel

consumption. This indicates that the blend is giving good performance compared with other blends.

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